

The Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence relating to Total Energy

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Abstract: This paper presents the mass-energy equation derived the sum of kinetic energy and potential energy (rest mass energy). This mass-energy equation is related to the Einstein's mass-energy equivalence noted in the special theory of relativity.

Keywords: classical mechanics, relativity, rest mass energy

Total Energy and Einstein's Mass-Energy Equation

The total energy is equal to the sum of kinetic energy and potential energy. Here, the potential energy is considered as rest mass energy noted in the special theory of relativity. Now, let us calculate the total energy of an object with mass (m) and velocity (v) that is related to the Einstein mass-energy equivalence [1-14].

Total Energy (E) = Kinetic Energy (K) + Potential Energy (P), i.e. $E = K + P$.

Here, $K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$ and $P = mgh$.

Let us prove that the potential energy or rest mass energy is equal to the kinetic energy.

$$P = mgh = mas. \quad (1)$$

$$s = ut + \frac{1}{2}at^2 \Rightarrow s = 0 + \frac{1}{2}at^2 \Rightarrow s = \frac{1}{2}at^2. \quad (2)$$

$$v^2 = u^2 + 2as \Rightarrow v^2 = 0 + 2as \Rightarrow v^2 = 2a\left(\frac{1}{2}at^2\right) \Rightarrow v^2 = a^2t^2. \quad (3)$$

By substituting the equation (2) in the equation (1), we get

$$P = ma \times s \Rightarrow P = ma \times \frac{1}{2}at^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}ma^2t^2. \quad (4)$$

By substituting the equation (3) in the equation (4), we conclude that

$$P = \frac{1}{2}ma^2t^2 \Rightarrow P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = K \quad (5)$$

Hence proved.

$$\text{Then, } E = K + P = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = mv^2. \quad (6)$$

If we consider that the velocity (v) is equal to the speed of light (c), then $E = mc^2$. But, the velocity (v) of any object with non-zero mass is less than the speed of light (c).

Therefore, $E = mc_v^2$, where $c_v < c$.

If there is a value c_u such that $c_u < c$, then $c_u < c_v < c$.

Hence, $E \neq mc^2$.

In addition, the following references [1-14] give more information regarding the energy of an object in motion.

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